

Seasonal Dynamics of Vegetation, Biomass, and Environmental Drivers in Semi-Arid Artemisia-ephemeral Foothill Rangelands of Uzbekistan: A Case Study of Using Remote Sensing and Field-Based Indicators

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Abstract

Understanding the ecological responses of vegetation to climate variability and soil conditions is critical for effective rangeland management in arid and semi-arid regions. This study examined the seasonal dynamics of vegetation, particularly *Artemisia diffusa*, in the semi-arid foothill rangelands of Uzbekistan over a three-year period (2021-2023). Utilizing a combination of field-based measurements and remote sensing techniques, we evaluated changes in aboveground biomass, foliar pigments, NDVI values, and associated climatic and soil parameters. Results revealed a strong relationship between precipitation and vegetation productivity. Higher spring precipitation in 2022 led to increased biomass accumulation and elevated NDVI values compared to the drier years of 2021 and 2023. Soil moisture in the upper 0-40 cm layer was found to be a critical limiting factor for vegetation development, with a strong correlation observed between soil moisture, foliar chlorophyll content, and NDVI. While ephemeral species contributed significantly to biomass and greenness in spring, *A. diffusa* dominated the vegetation structure in summer and autumn, with productivity declining under high temperatures and reduced humidity. These findings highlight the seasonal interplay between climate, soil, and vegetation and demonstrate the utility of NDVI as a tool for monitoring rangeland condition. However, caution is needed when interpreting spring NDVI data, as temporary greening from ephemeral species may mask early signs of degradation. This study underscores the importance of integrated approaches combining remote sensing and field observations to improve our understanding of rangeland ecosystems and support sustainable land management strategies under changing climate conditions.

Keywords: *Artemisia diffusa*; NDVI; rangeland monitoring; seasonal dynamics; soil moisture; precipitation; aboveground biomass; remote sensing; semi-arid ecosystems; climate-vegetation interactions; Uzbekistan; ephemeroïds

Introduction

In recent decades, rangelands have experienced extensive degradation primarily due to overgrazing and various human-induced disturbances, leading to severe soil erosion and a decline in land quality. As a result, both forage production and livestock industries have been negatively impacted (Christmann et al., 2015; Han et al., 2008). This issue is particularly pronounced in the foothill rangelands of Central Asian countries, where continuous, unregulated land use has led to a noticeable decline in plant diversity and biomass (Mirzabaev et al., 2016; Jing et al., 2013). Globally, land degradation and soil deterioration have been recognized as significant threats to the sustainability of rangeland ecosystems (Muminov et al., 2024, Mukimov et al., 2021, Rajabov et al., 2020, Nosirov, 2003). Without proper management, intensive grazing and expanding human populations further accelerate the loss of productive grasslands (Gintzburger et al., 2003; Nosyrov, 2003; Mirzabaev et al., 2016, Rajabov, 2009). However, accurately assessing the degree of rangeland degradation, as well as quantifying vegetation coverage and productivity under growing human pressures, remains a major challenge. Plant growth is strongly influenced by interactions between multiple environmental factors, including seasonal climatic variations. These seasonal shifts directly and indirectly affect vegetation growth patterns. Long-term studies focusing on the physiological responses of vegetation to grazing gradients in arid and semi-arid regions remain limited. To evaluate plant health and productivity, various vegetation indices have been developed, with the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) being one of the most widely used (Rouse et al., 1974). NDVI, calculated as $(\rho_{IR} - \rho_R) / (\rho_{IR} + \rho_R)$, where ρ_{IR} and ρ_R represent near-infrared and red reflectance respectively, correlates strongly with green biomass and vegetation coverage (Justice et al., 1985). Green plants exhibit specific reflectance characteristics in the red (0.63–0.69 μm) and near-infrared (0.76–0.90 μm) bands, making these spectral regions highly valuable for assessing plant vigor, photosynthetic activity, and canopy structure (Gibson et al., 2000). Although NDVI has been widely adopted for monitoring vegetation dynamics and aboveground net primary production (ANPP) (Rajabov et al., 2020; Pettorelli et al., 2005), many studies have primarily focused on long-term environmental and physiological trends. Some research in arid regions has reported positive correlations between rainfall and NDVI (Rajabov et al., 2020; Paudel & Andersen, 2010), but comprehensive investigations exploring the chain relationships among NDVI, seasonal climate variations, plant characteristics, and soil properties remain scarce. Remote sensing (RS) offers significant advantages for monitoring the physiological state of vegetation across large areas, especially where long-term ground-based observations are impractical due to time, labor, and cost constraints. We hypothesize that strong chain correlations exist between biological and environmental variables in these rangelands. Precipitation and soil moisture are key drivers of vegetation growth, and these influences are reflected in NDVI values (Muminov et al., 2016; Rajabov et al., 2020). However, unmanaged grazing and human interventions may disrupt these natural relationships, emphasizing the need for reliable, cost-effective, and precise monitoring tools for vegetation cover and productivity assessment in arid rangelands. In this study, we employed remote sensing to assess rangeland productivity, degradation levels, and vegetation dynamics. These data not only support ecosystem monitoring but also aid in developing effective restoration strategies to counteract ecosystem imbalances. Satellite imagery provides extensive information on vegetation cover and land use patterns (Juliev et al. 2019), and understanding the links between NDVI, biomass, climate, and soil conditions may enhance the

application of remote monitoring techniques (Star et al., 2010). In Central Asia, approximately 77% of potentially usable land is at risk of vegetation degradation (REAP, 2006). Despite this, field-based assessments remain limited, making it difficult to fully understand the complex relationships between environmental conditions and vegetation responses. Therefore, the objectives of this study are: (1) to investigate the effects of environmental factors on plant growth and their seasonal variations; (2) to examine the seasonal relationships between climate variables and NDVI, with specific focus on biomass, canopy cover, chlorophyll, and carotenoid contents; and (3) to explore the links between seasonal precipitation, soil moisture, and NDVI in foothill rangelands. The findings of this research aim to support decision-makers in evaluating vegetation cover, ecosystem productivity, and degradation risks in arid and semi-arid rangelands vulnerable to ongoing degradation.

1. Materials and Methods

1.1. Study Area

This study was conducted in the semi-arid Aktau foothill rangelands located in Samarkand Province, Uzbekistan (40°09'N, 66°39'E) (Fig. 1). The landscape features a variety of elevations, ranging from gently rolling hills to steeper mountain slopes. The total study area spans approximately 4,300 km², representing about 9.5% of Uzbekistan's territory. Elevations in this region vary from 500 to 1,600 meters above sea level (Gintzburger et al., 2003). The Aktau range falls under the continental subtropical climate zone of Central Asia (Gintzburger et al., 2003; Rakhmatullaev, 1991, Muminov et al., 2016). Due to its position near the western Tien-Shan mountains and bordering the Kyzyl Kum desert, the area experiences significant desert climatic influences. During summer, hot air masses raise temperatures to 30–35°C in the mountains and up to 42–43°C in the foothills (Fig. 2). The average July temperature in the mountains is approximately 24°C, with annual precipitation ranging between 350 and 400 mm (Rakhmatullaev, 1991). The growing season typically begins in late February or early March and continues until September, lasting 260 to 270 days. The predominant soil type in the area is light sierozem, often featuring gypsiferous layers or stony deposits (Gintzburger et al., 2003, Nosyrov, 2003, Mukimov et al., 2021, Rajabov et al., 2020). These soils are poor in organic matter, containing less than 1%. The forage yield of these

rangelands

Figure 1. Location of the study area within the semi-arid Aktau foothill rangelands, Samarkand Province, Uzbekistan. Blue pentagrams indicate fixed sampling sites established for ecological and vegetation monitoring

Figure 7. Seasonal dynamics of NDVI and climatic variables during the plant-growing season (spring (March-May), summer (June-August), autumn (September-November) over three years (2021–2023). Variables include seasonal sum of precipitation (SSP, mm), minimum air humidity (AHmin, %), and mean daily air temperature (MAT, °C).

between 300 and 700 kg of dry matter per hectare, depending on annual climatic conditions (Gintzburger et al., 2003; Mukimov et al., 2021). Heavy grazing pressure is most intense during spring and summer when livestock freely graze, while it decreases sharply during autumn and winter, except for continued grazing on *Artemisia diffusa*. The local population numbers approximately 115,000 people, with a total livestock count of 413,766 animals, making overgrazing a primary factor contributing to land degradation.

1.2. Vegetation

The vegetation in the study area is primarily dominated year-round by *Artemisia diffusa*, with sparse occurrences of species such as *Iris songarica* and *Alhagi pseudalhagi*. In spring, additional ephemeral and ephemeroïd species such as *Poa bulbosa*, *Carex pachystylis*, *Salsola spp.*, and *Holosteum umbellatum* emerge, contributing to the seasonal plant diversity (Gintzburger et al., 2003;

Zokirov, 1971; Akhmedov et al., 2021). These ephemeral species account for approximately 15–20% of the plant cover in Artemisia-ephemeral rangelands (Muminov et al., 2016, Akhmedov et al., 2021). In certain foothill regions, scattered woody plants such as *Pistacia vera spinosissima*, *Punica granatum*, *Atraphaxis spinosa*, and *Zygophyllum gontscharovii* are also present (Burygin, 1976; Gintzburger et al., 2003). The northern slopes, receiving more precipitation, support dense stands of *Carex pachystylis*. Other commonly observed species include *Festuca spp.*, viviparous *Poa bulbosa*, *Hordeum bulbosum*, *Stipa spp.*, *Aegilops triuncialis*, and *Bromus tectorum* (Gintzburger et al., 2003; Akhmedov et al., 2021). Due to its dominance, *Artemisia diffusa* was selected for detailed analysis in this study.

Figure 3. Seasonal variation in ground cover within Artemisia-dominated ephemeral rangelands.

Table 1. The growth period of the main dominant plants in the study area. The shaded green area represents the growth period of the plant. (Source: Adapted from Gintzburger et al.2003; Muminov et al. 2016)

No	Plant species	Jan.	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
The main dominant plant species													
1.	<i>Artemisia diffusa L.</i>												
2.	<i>Carex pachystylis L</i>												
3.	<i>Poa bulbosa L.</i>												
4.	<i>Bromus tectorum L.</i>												
Sparse-distributed plant species (ephemeroids)													
1.	<i>Iris longiscapa Ldh</i>												
2.	<i>Alhagi pseudalhagi (MB) Desv.</i>												

1.3. Meteorological and Soil Data Collection

To characterize the climatic conditions of each study site, mean monthly precipitation and temperature data were obtained from the Climatic Research Unit Time-Series (CRU TS3.10) dataset (Harris et al., 2014). In addition, meteorological data, including daily mean air temperature, minimum relative humidity, and precipitation for the period 2021–2023, were acquired from the relevant national meteorological stations located near the study areas. These complementary datasets provided reliable climate inputs essential for analyzing both long-term and recent environmental trends. Soil samples were collected monthly from each sampling plot at depths of 0-40 cm. These samples were divided into two parts for analysis. Soil moisture content was determined by drying the samples for 48 hours in a drying oven. Nitrate concentrations were

measured based on the interaction with disulfofenol acid to produce trinitrophenol (picric acid), which forms a yellow complex in alkaline conditions. The intensity of this color, proportional to nitrate content, was measured using a photo-colorimeter (Minayeff, 2001).

1.4. Pilot Site Design, Vegetation Monitoring, and Assessment of Leaf Pigments

To investigate the effects of livestock grazing intensity on rangeland vegetation, three pilot sites were established along a gradient of grazing pressure, determined by their proximity to a settlement (Muminov et al. 2016). The first site was situated close to the settlement (N 40°08'50.21", E 66°38'50.56"), the second at an intermediate distance (N 40°09'18.70", E 66°39'12.37"), and the third approximately 2 km away from the settlement (N 40°09'37.68", E 66°39'27.34"). These sites reflected varying degrees of grazing intensity and associated vegetation degradation. Each site was further characterized based on vegetation cover into three types: sparse, moderate, and dense. Within each site, three replicate plots were established approximately 100 meters apart to account for small-scale environmental variability, resulting in a total of nine sampling plots spaced roughly 1,000 meters apart (see Fig. 1 and 3). Subplot locations were selected based on their distance from the livestock concentration point—specifically at 500 m., 1500 m., and 2000 m. serving as proxies for grazing intensity gradients. The geographical coordinates of all plots and subplots were recorded using a Garmin GPS 12 XL device to ensure spatial accuracy and consistency across survey periods. Field-based vegetation monitoring was carried out monthly from 2021 to 2023. At each subplot, the following vegetation parameters were measured: species composition, aboveground biomass, vegetation cover, plant density, and leaf pigment concentrations (chlorophyll *a+b* and carotenoids), with special attention given to perennial species. The study area's vegetation primarily consists of semi-shrub and ephemeral plant communities, with *Artemisia diffusa* as the dominant species. To assess the physiological status of vegetation, chemical analyses were performed on *A. diffusa* samples. Chlorophyll *a+b* and carotenoid contents were quantified using an SF-26 spectrophotometer with 100% acetone extraction, following the Holm–Wettstein method as cited in Tretyakov (1990). Vegetation structure was characterized using 10 m × 10 m geobotanical transect plots, with three replications at each of the nine sites. Within each 10 m² plot, all shrub individuals were counted and classified into three size classes (small, medium, and large), based on plant height and crown diameter. For each species and size class, three representative shrubs were harvested and separated into woody and green biomass components. Total shrub biomass per plot was calculated by combining species-specific density data with average biomass values from the sampled individuals. The canopy cover of *A. diffusa* was estimated using the line intercept method along all four edges of each 10 m × 10 m plot. In addition, the biomass of ephemeral and ephemeroid species was measured using 50 cm × 10 cm quadrats, randomly placed within each plot with three replicates per site. This comprehensive approach enabled an integrated assessment of both structural and functional attributes of plant communities under varying grazing intensities.

1.5. Image Preprocessing and NDVI Calculation

This study used Google Earth Engine (GEE) for preprocessing satellite images and computing the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) for the Tashkent region of Uzbekistan. The analysis focused on Landsat data spanning the period from 2021 to 2023. Surface reflectance imagery from Landsat 5 (LT05) and Landsat 7 (LE07) was utilized, as these sensors were actively capturing data during the target years.

Preprocessing of Landsat Imagery

All Landsat scenes were filtered to the predefined area of interest (AOI). Cloud-contaminated pixels were removed using the QA_PIXEL quality assurance band. Cloud, cloud shadow, snow, and cirrus masks were generated using bitwise operators to exclude low-quality pixels from analysis.

Radiometric corrections were applied to convert raw digital numbers to surface reflectance values using sensor-specific scale factors and offsets. Spectral bands were then renamed uniformly across sensors as: blue, green, red, near-infrared (nir), shortwave infrared 1 (swir1), shortwave infrared 2 (swir2), and land surface temperature (lst). This standardization ensured compatibility across both Landsat 5 and Landsat 7 datasets.

NDVI Calculation

NDVI was computed for each preprocessed image using the standard formula:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{(\text{NIR} - \text{RED})}{(\text{NIR} + \text{RED})}$$

where NIR and RED refer to the near-infrared and red bands, respectively. The NDVI layer was added as an additional band to each image in the collection.

Seasonal NDVI Composites

To analyze vegetation dynamics at a seasonal scale, three seasonal composites were generated for each year-spring (March to May), summer (June to August), and autumn (September to November). For each season, median NDVI values were calculated using all available cloud-free images. These composites provided a representative view of seasonal vegetation conditions during the years 2021, 2022, and 2023.

Data Export

Each seasonal NDVI composite was exported from Google Earth Engine to Google Drive in GeoTIFF format at a 30-meter spatial resolution. These images served as the input for further geospatial and temporal analysis of vegetation trends in the study area.

1.6. Statistical Analysis

The study design included three sites with three replicates each. The Least Significant Difference (LSD) test to determine statistical significance at $P < 0.01$. Pearson correlation analysis was used to explore relationships between NDVI values, vegetation parameters, soil properties, and climatic factors during the growing seasons. All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS 19.0. Figures were generated with Sigma Plot 14.0. Data are presented as means \pm standard error.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Seasonal Patterns in Growth Dynamics and Biomass Accumulation of *Artemisia diffusa*

The phenological development of the dominant rangeland species, *Artemisia diffusa*, begins in late February and concludes by early June, spanning a vegetative cycle of approximately 230-237 days. This life cycle duration aligns with previous findings (Gintzburger et al., 2003). From 2021 to 2023, *A. diffusa* exhibited pronounced seasonal fluctuations in canopy cover, with the lowest values recorded in spring, a gradual increase through summer, and the highest coverage observed in autumn (Fig. 5C). The year 2022 showed the most substantial canopy expansion, closely associated with elevated spring precipitation. Enhanced moisture availability during this period contributed to more vigorous vegetative development compared to the drier conditions observed in 2021 and 2023. Nevertheless, as the growing season progressed, soil moisture decreased sharply during summer and

Figure 4. Seasonal NDVI map views of the study area during spring, summer, and autumn, illustrating spatial variations in vegetation cover across different phenological phases.

Figure 5. Seasonal relationships between NDVI and (A) total aboveground biomass (kg/ha), (B) annual green biomass (kg/ha), (C) percent cover, and (D) foliar chlorophyll content of *Artemisia diffusa* across spring, summer, and autumn during the 2021-2023 growing seasons.

autumn, particularly affecting the productivity of ephemeral and ephemeroïd plant groups, thus limiting the overall community biomass. This moisture is a critical factor influencing the physiological activity and seasonal development of vegetation. Moreover, a significant relationship

was observed between soil moisture and the content of mobile (changeable) nitrogen, both of which are correlated with NDVI values (Fig. 5). Aboveground biomass trends of *A. diffusa* paralleled the seasonal pattern of canopy coverage. Both total biomass (TBM) and green biomass (GBM) increased during summer, followed by a decline in autumn. Peak biomass values occurred in 2022, likely driven by favorable climatic conditions in spring. These trends were also reflected in the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), which peaked in 2022, signaling improved vegetation vigor and health. Maximum aboveground biomass accumulation occurred in summer and was primarily attributable to *A. diffusa*, as ephemeral species were no longer present beyond spring. In spring, however, both *A. diffusa* and seasonal species such as *Poa bulbosa* and *Carex pachystylis* contributed significantly to biomass accumulation. During summer and autumn, the vegetation community was largely composed of *A. diffusa*, which dominated biomass production (Fig. 3). NDVI values were highest in spring, reflecting the combined photosynthetic activity of *A. diffusa* and ephemeral species. In the later seasons, NDVI primarily represented *A. diffusa* alone. This seasonal transition in vegetative composition was clearly consistent with changes in measured biomass. The seasonal variation in biomass was closely aligned with NDVI values. While both GBM and TBM in spring were influenced by the mixed-species community, the biomass observed in summer and autumn was predominantly driven by *A. diffusa*. These seasonal trends are clearly depicted in Figure 3, where *A. diffusa* biomass peaks in the summer season. A statistically significant positive correlation ($P < 0.01$) was found between NDVI and both total and green aboveground biomass of the entire vegetation community. However, the correlation between NDVI and *A. diffusa* biomass alone was only moderate (Fig. 5D), indicating that NDVI more accurately captures vegetation dynamics when multiple species are active, particularly in spring. Spatial variation in *A. diffusa* distribution was influenced by both topographic heterogeneity and anthropogenic pressures such as grazing intensity. Plant density was generally lower during spring and autumn compared to summer, possibly due to environmental constraints and land-use stressors. A strong inverse relationship was found between *A. diffusa* canopy cover and NDVI in 2022 ($P < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.75$), with similar patterns also noted in 2021 and 2023, suggesting that areas with denser *A. diffusa* coverage may experience saturation effects in spectral reflectance.

2.2. Soil Moisture Dynamics and Climatic Influences on Vegetation Productivity

Soil moisture exhibited a strong and positive correlation with NDVI values, emphasizing its critical role in influencing vegetation productivity across the study area. While precipitation is undoubtedly important, several studies, including Jing et al. (2013), suggest that direct soil moisture availability may serve as a more reliable indicator of plant growth than rainfall alone. In this semi-arid region, the soil profile typically extends to a depth of 40-60 cm, with the lower layers characterized by coarse gravel and rock fragments. This structure limits the soil's water-holding capacity and accelerates moisture loss in the absence of precipitation, making soil moisture highly dependent on recent rainfall events. Measurements showed that soil moisture in the upper 0-40 cm layer was relatively high during spring but declined sharply during the summer and autumn seasons (Fig. 5). This decline has direct implications for vegetation physiology and seasonal development, as water availability becomes a major limiting factor during the hotter, drier months. Seasonal climatic variations were found to play a key regulatory role in shaping both ecological processes and plant physiological responses. Spring is characterized by moderate air temperatures and higher air humidity, creating favorable conditions for vegetation growth, particularly for ephemeral species.

Figure 6. Relationships between Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) with soil moisture and soil changeable nitrogen in vegetation growing seasons (spring, summer, autumn)

Figure 8. Mutual relationships among natural components in the study area: (A) 2021, (B) 2022, (C) 2023, and (D) average values over the three years (2021–2023). Variables include: NDVI-Normalized Difference Vegetation Index; GBM*-green aboveground wet biomass of *Artemisia diffusa*; TBM*-total aboveground wet biomass of *Artemisia diffusa* (green plus non-green biomass); GBM-green aboveground wet biomass of total vegetation; TBM -total aboveground wet biomass (green plus non-green biomass) of total vegetation; CHL-foliar chlorophyll content of *Artemisia diffusa*; CAR-foliar carotenoid content of *Artemisia diffusa*; PC-percent coverage of dominant plant *Artemisia diffusa*; SM-soil moisture; SN-soil changeable nitrogen (NO_3^- -N); Precipitation-annual seasonal precipitation; Temperature-mean air temperature.

Conversely, during summer and autumn, rising temperatures and significant reductions in air

humidity exacerbate soil desiccation, thereby limiting vegetation growth and productivity. NDVI values were consistently higher in spring, largely due to the presence of ephemeral vegetation. However, this seasonal vegetation cover may obscure degradation signals during this period. In contrast, NDVI data from summer and autumn provided clearer insights into the degradation status of *Artemisia diffusa*-dominated landscapes (Fig. 3 and 4). Notably, in spring 2022, elevated NDVI values aligned with increased precipitation levels, facilitating rapid regeneration of both *A. diffusa* and ephemeral species (Fig. 3). The study identified statistically significant correlations ($P < 0.01$) between NDVI, soil moisture, and available (changeable) nitrogen, reinforcing the potential of NDVI as a reliable proxy for assessing rangeland condition and productivity. These interconnected relationships among climatic, edaphic, and biological variables offer a robust framework for evaluating ecosystem function and resilience in semi-arid environments. Additionally, a strong positive correlation was observed between seasonal NDVI and seasonal precipitation (SSP), confirming the direct influence of rainfall on vegetation greenness. NDVI also exhibited a positive association with minimum air humidity (AH), while a negative correlation was found with mean daily air temperature (MAT) (Fig. 8). These findings collectively underscore the pivotal role of seasonal climatic drivers—particularly precipitation and humidity—in determining the spatial and temporal patterns of vegetation activity in semi-arid foothill rangelands.

DISCUSSION

Seasonal Biomass Dynamics and Climatic Influences on *Artemisia diffusa*-Dominated Semi-Arid Rangelands

The seasonal and interannual vegetation dynamics in the semi-arid Aktau foothill rangelands are strongly influenced by climatic variability, particularly precipitation and its effects on soil moisture. The dominant species, *Artemisia diffusa*, initiates aboveground growth in late February and completes its life cycle by early June, maintaining a growing period of approximately 230–237 days (Gintzburger et al., 2003, Rajabov et al., 2020, Muminov et al., 2016). The phenological and productivity patterns of *Artemisia diffusa* across the 2021–2023 observation period reveal clear seasonal and interannual variability closely tied to climatic conditions, particularly precipitation and soil moisture availability. Canopy cover of *A. diffusa* exhibited a distinct seasonal trajectory, with lower values in spring, increasing through summer, and reaching a peak in autumn. Among the study years, 2022 stood out with the highest vegetation cover, corresponding to increased spring rainfall. This enhanced moisture availability early in the growing season likely promoted more robust growth of *A. diffusa* and ephemeral species, compared to the drier conditions observed in 2021 and 2023. Despite the productive spring period, limited soil moisture in summer and autumn constrained the growth of ephemeral and ephemeroïd species, which are highly sensitive to water availability. Consequently, the aboveground biomass during these drier seasons was dominated by *A. diffusa*, which demonstrated a capacity to maintain biomass production under reduced moisture conditions. The total and green biomass values (TBM and GBM) for 2022 exceeded those of the other two years, a pattern that closely paralleled the NDVI values, which were also highest in 2022. This alignment suggests that NDVI effectively captured the temporal fluctuations in vegetation productivity driven by climatic variability. In spring, biomass accumulation resulted from the combined growth of *A. diffusa* and early-season ephemeral species such as *Poa bulbosa* and *Carex pachystylis*. These species contributed significantly to both green and total biomass, enhancing NDVI values during this period. However, by early summer, most ephemeroïds had completed their life cycles, leaving *A. diffusa* as

the primary contributor to vegetation structure and biomass. This shift was reflected in both NDVI values and biomass composition, which were increasingly dominated by *A. diffusa* during the later part of the growing season. The seasonal NDVI dynamics mirrored these vegetation changes. Peak NDVI values in spring can be attributed to the simultaneous greening of both perennial and ephemeral components of the plant community. In contrast, summer and autumn NDVI values reflected the presence and physiological status of *A. diffusa* alone, as the ephemeral community had senesced. The favorable climatic conditions of 2022, particularly higher spring precipitation, led to the most pronounced NDVI responses, underlining the sensitivity of NDVI to interannual climatic variability. Statistical analysis revealed a strong positive correlation ($P < 0.01$) between NDVI and the seasonal total and green biomass of the vegetation, reinforcing the index's utility as a reliable proxy for estimating productivity in semi-arid rangelands. However, correlations between NDVI and the biomass of *A. diffusa* alone were relatively weaker. This indicates that NDVI may be more responsive to the combined greenness of diverse and active plant communities rather than to dominant species in isolation—especially during early growing stages when ephemeral species contribute substantially to canopy cover and chlorophyll content. Spatial variation in *A. diffusa* density and percent cover was also observed, likely influenced by topographic heterogeneity and varying levels of grazing pressure. Notably, plant density was typically lower in spring and autumn than in summer. Grazing, particularly in spring when plants are still establishing, may suppress growth and contribute to spatial variability. Interestingly, a strong negative correlation was found between percent cover of *A. diffusa* and NDVI, particularly in 2022 ($P < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.75$), with consistent patterns across 2021 and 2023. This suggests that denser stands of *A. diffusa* may not necessarily translate to higher NDVI values, possibly due to structural or physiological traits of the species, such as reduced chlorophyll content or less reflective canopy surfaces. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of spring precipitation in determining vegetation productivity and highlight the role of NDVI in capturing seasonal vegetation dynamics in semi-arid ecosystems. The data further emphasize the ecological significance of ephemeral species during the early growing season and the utility of integrating NDVI with field-based biomass and vegetation structure assessments for effective rangeland monitoring.

Climatic Influences and Soil Moisture as Determinants of Rangeland Productivity

Understanding the dynamics of vegetation in arid and semi-arid ecosystems requires evaluating the complex interactions between climatic conditions, soil properties, and plant responses. This study highlighted the central role of precipitation and soil moisture in shaping vegetation productivity in the semi-arid foothill rangelands of Uzbekistan, particularly in the Aktau region. Our findings demonstrated that soil moisture is a critical determinant of vegetation growth and physiological activity. Despite the importance of rainfall as a general driver, it is the actual availability of soil moisture in the upper 40 cm of the soil profile that more directly influences plant vitality. The soil in the study area, characterized by a shallow (40-60 cm) loamy layer overlying gravel and rock, has limited water retention capacity. As a result, the absence of rainfall leads to rapid soil desiccation, especially during the hot and dry summer and autumn months. This explains the observed seasonal decline in soil moisture following the relatively wet spring period. Vegetation indicators such as NDVI and biomass accumulation closely followed this seasonal moisture pattern. NDVI values peaked in spring, coinciding with higher soil moisture levels and the presence of both perennial (e.g., *Artemisia diffusa*) and ephemeral species (e.g., *Poa bulbosa*, *Carex pachystylis*). This multi-species vegetation cover increased the greenness signal detected by satellite imagery. However, NDVI values

declined markedly in summer and autumn, reflecting the dominance of *A. diffusa* under moisture-limited conditions and the senescence of ephemeral plants. Interestingly, while spring NDVI values were higher, this often masked early degradation signals due to the temporary greening effects of ephemeral species. In contrast, summer and autumn NDVI values offered a more reliable assessment of rangeland condition, particularly with regard to long-term changes in *A. diffusa* coverage and health. The highest NDVI and biomass values recorded in 2022 were linked to increased precipitation in that year, supporting the close relationship between rainfall patterns and vegetation performance. Statistical analysis confirmed significant correlations between NDVI, soil moisture, green biomass, and changeable soil nitrogen (NO_3^- -N) ($P < 0.01$). These interdependencies emphasize the utility of NDVI not only as a greenness indicator but also as a proxy for broader ecological functioning. The relationship between NDVI and foliar chlorophyll content of *A. diffusa* further supports this interpretation, as chlorophyll levels directly influence plant photosynthesis and reflect overall plant health. Moreover, climatic factors such as air temperature and humidity played essential roles in regulating soil moisture and plant physiology. During spring, moderate temperatures and higher humidity levels created favorable conditions for vegetation growth. However, during summer and autumn, increased temperatures and reduced humidity accelerated evapotranspiration and soil drying, exacerbating stress on the vegetation. Notably, NDVI exhibited a positive correlation with minimum air humidity and a negative correlation with mean air temperature, reinforcing the notion that heat and aridity limit vegetation activity during the dry season. Overall, these findings point to a chain of ecological relationships in which precipitation influences soil moisture, which in turn affects nitrogen availability, vegetation productivity, and NDVI patterns. This interconnected framework supports the use of remote sensing indicators, particularly NDVI, for effective rangeland monitoring and degradation assessment. The study confirms that integrating NDVI with ground-based measurements of soil and plant variables provides a comprehensive approach to evaluating rangeland health and guiding management decisions in dryland environments.

Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of vegetation dynamics, climatic influences, and soil-vegetation interactions in the semi-arid foothill rangelands of Uzbekistan over a three-year period (2021–2023). The results clearly demonstrate that vegetation productivity, particularly of the dominant species *Artemisia diffusa*, is highly sensitive to seasonal climatic variations, especially precipitation and soil moisture availability. The seasonal dynamics of NDVI, aboveground biomass, and canopy cover were strongly linked to fluctuations in rainfall and air humidity. Spring conditions, characterized by moderate temperatures and higher precipitation, favored the growth of both *A. diffusa* and ephemeral plant communities, resulting in higher NDVI values and biomass accumulation. In contrast, the summer and autumn seasons exhibited reduced vegetation activity due to elevated temperatures, lower humidity, and declining soil moisture content. These conditions limited plant physiological processes and led to decreased productivity, particularly in the absence of ephemerals. Soil moisture in the upper 40 cm of the soil profile emerged as a key factor influencing plant growth and NDVI values. The observed strong correlations among NDVI, soil moisture, foliar chlorophyll, and soil nitrogen content (NO_3^- -N) highlight the interconnectedness of climate, soil, and vegetation components in driving ecosystem function. These relationships provide a valuable foundation for using NDVI and other remote sensing indices as effective tools for monitoring rangeland health and detecting early signs of land degradation. Importantly, the study underscores that NDVI alone may overestimate vegetation conditions in spring due to the temporary greening

effects of ephemeral species. Therefore, integrating NDVI with ground-based measurements of soil moisture, biomass, and plant composition is essential for a more accurate and holistic assessment of rangeland status. By elucidating the eco-physiological responses of vegetation to climate variability and soil properties, this research offers critical insights for sustainable rangeland management in arid and semi-arid regions. The findings support the use of remote sensing technologies to inform adaptive land use strategies and guide efforts aimed at mitigating the impacts of climate change and anthropogenic pressures on fragile dryland ecosystems.

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